

GIANCE Project Kickstarts on October 1st: Pioneering Sustainable Graphene-based Solutions for Environmental Challenges

Barcelona, October 2023 - GIANCE, a groundbreaking research project, officially commenced on October 1st, marking a significant step toward addressing environmental challenges with innovative solutions.

About GIANCE

GIANCE is an ambitious initiative that seeks to establish a holistic, integrated, and industry-driven platform with a clear focus on improving sustainable materials and their real-world applications. Our project is dedicated to designing, developing, and scaling up the next generation of cost-effective, sustainable, lightweight, and recyclable graphene and related materials (GRM)-based multifunctional composites, coatings, foams, and membranes (GRM-bM).

These advanced materials are engineered to possess enhanced properties such as thermal, mechanical, and chemical attributes, providing functionalities like wear resistance, corrosion resistance, chemical and fire resistance, hardness, impact resistance, high-temperature resistance, structural health monitoring, and ultralow friction surfaces.

Furthermore, GIANCE is committed to advancing manufacturing processes, improving synthesis and stability, and reducing environmental impact. These capabilities will create strong connections with end-users, facilitating the development and qualification of commercial propositions to high Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs).

To give you a glimpse of GIANCE project's potential impact, GIANCE is designed to be a robust catalyst in the EU GRM scene, fully equipped by major industries to elevate GRM to the next level of applications to strengthen companies in terms of competitiveness and growth potential in line with the needs of EU and global markets. By stimulating new manufactured high-value products and utilizing GRM in major civilian sectors such as transportation (automotive and aerospace), energy (hydrogen economy), and water treatment, GIANCE has the potential to yield significant economic and societal benefits. GIANCE's work directly supports the innovation output and industrialization efforts of the Graphene Flagship initiative, paving the way for the accumulation of knowledge to impact the European Union's industry and society.

GIANCE's Consortium

Our consortium comprises 23 partners from 10 countries, representing the entire value chain. We have brought together leading Original Equipment Manufacturers (OEMs), large industries, world-class research and educational organizations, and innovative SMEs.

Toward a Sustainable Future

GIANCE is strategically designed to maximize its impact on industries and society at large, making substantial contributions to the evolving field of graphene and related materials. Our ultimate goal is to usher in a strong EU value chain that can transform technological advancements from TRL4-5 into concrete innovation opportunities and production capabilities (TRL6-7). This positioning will grant us first-mover market advantages at scale in the defined industrial sectors.

For further information about GIANCE, please follow our [Linkedin page](#).

Consortium

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